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Bi(bli)oArch: An open-access bibliographic database for human bioarchaeological studies in the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East

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Abstract

The current paper presents Bi(bli)oArch, a free online bibliographic database for human bioarchaeology in the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East (EMME); a geographic region at the crossroads of three continents and a melting pot of diverse civilizations throughout human evolution. The aim of Bi(bli)oArch is to promote human bioarchaeological studies in the region and facilitate meta-analyses by making the titles of available studies more easily findable by international scholars. At the moment, many publications are difficult to identify, as they appear in national languages of the region and/or in outputs such as national conference proceedings, graduate theses, and monograph appendices. This paper presents the main functionalities of Bi(bli)oArch, briefly outlines some key trends in EMME bioarchaeology as revealed through the 3,521 papers that are currently included in this database, and invites scholars working in the EMME to contribute to this initiative so that Bi(bli)oArch develops into a standard bibliographic bioarchaeological resource for the region.

Keywords: bioarchaeology; human skeletal analysis; bibliography; Eastern Mediterranean; Middle East

1. Introduction

Osteoarchaeological research focusses on the study of human skeletal remains from archaeological contexts (Larsen, 2015; Nikita, 2017). Given the complex biosocial nature of humans, bioarchaeology is among the disciplines that would greatly benefit from large comparative studies which would allow exploring the impact of diverse biological, natural environmental, socio-political and other factors in more recent human evolution. Nonetheless, the number of osteoarchaeological data syntheses and meta-analyses is particularly small, even though their thematic diversity highlights the potential of this approach in addressing past mobility, the evolution of diseases and other important aspects of life in the past with implications in the present (e.g. Leppard et al., 2020; Müller and Hussein, 2017; Setzer, 2014).

The first step in any meta-analysis is bibliographic research, which helps refine subsequent research questions and approaches. As such, it is imperative to ensure that relevant research is thorough and all key publications have been correctly identified (Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Katz, 2009). A serious challenge in bibliographic research is that many publications are often difficult to retrieve, as they appear in various national languages and/or in outputs that are not easily identified by traditional search engines, such as national conference proceedings, graduate theses, and monograph appendices. This is an issue that also characterizes bioarchaeological bibliographical research in the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East (EMME); a geographic region at the crossroads of three continents and a melting pot of diverse civilizations throughout human evolution.

In an attempt to overcome this limitation and open the way for more synthetic bioarchaeological studies in the EMME, following the example of such studies in the western hemisphere (Steckel and Rose, 2002; Steckel et al., 2002), the authors of this paper developed Bi(bli)oArch, a free online bibliographic database for EMME bioarchaeology. Bi(bli)oArch aims at promoting bioarchaeological research in the region by making human bioarchaeology papers more easily discoverable. To stress this communal philosophy, Bi(bli)oArch is a free tool and all content is distributed under the terms of a Creative Commons license (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0). The aim of the current communication is to present this initiative to the international research community so as to maximize the visibility and use of this resource, but also to invite scholars working in the EMME to contribute to this initiative so that Bi(bli)oArch evolves into a standard bibliographic bioarchaeological resource for the region.

2. Using Bi(bli)oArch

Bi(bli)oArch is a bibliographic database for human bioarchaeological studies in the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East (EMME), which can be accessed at <https://www.biblioarch.com/>. Information on the architecture of this web database is given in Supplement 1. Bi(bli)oArch currently contains 3,521 publications on human skeletal remains; however, it does not include

papers on mortuary/funerary archaeology if they contain no explicit presentation of human skeletal data.

The publication titles were retrieved through a thorough research in multiple sources. First, our team checked the table of contents of all leading international journals in bioarchaeology, physical anthropology, archaeological science, anthropological archaeology and palaeopathology (e.g. International Journal of Osteoarchaeology, HOMO, American Journal of Physical Anthropology, Journal of Archaeological Science, Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports, International Journal of Paleopathology, Journal of Anthropological Archaeology, Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences, Dental Anthropology, Anthropologischer Anzeiger, Bulletins et Memoires de la Societé d'Anthropologie de Paris). Then, the contents of regional journals with thematic linked to bioarchaeology (Bioarchaeology of the Near East) or the anthropological and archaeological sciences more generally (e.g. Antropoloji, Anthropologie, Arkeometri Sonuçları Toplantısı, Anatolica, Türk Tarih Kurumu Yayinlari, Mitekufat Haeven, Paléorient, Journal of Mediterranean Anthropology and Archaeology, Collegium Antropologicum, Belleten, Bulletin d'Archéologie et d'Architecture Libanaise, Sumer, Mediterranean Archaeology and Archaeometry) were examined. A detailed list of all journals that contain papers included in Bi(bli)oArch is given in Supplement 2. This journal-centered research was complemented by a systematic search via Google Scholar using combinations of the keywords 'osteoarchaeology', 'bioarchaeology', 'human skeletal analysis', 'palaeopathology', 'ancient DNA', 'isotopes', 'biodistance', 'taphonomy' coupled with each of the modern countries that comprise the EMME as well as the terms 'Eastern Mediterranean', 'Middle East', 'Levant', and 'Arabian Peninsula'. Following this step, the Reference list in each of the publications identified was checked so as to retrieve additional titles of interest. Moreover, the search options in academia.edu and ResearchGate were used to identify papers employing the same keywords as above for Google Scholar. Finally, the academia.edu and ResearchGate profiles and associated publications of specific authors the names of which repeatedly appeared in the previous steps of our research were examined. This final step was particularly useful in identifying publications in conference proceedings and monographs not published in English.

The Bi(bli)oArch database chronologically covers skeletal assemblages from Paleolithic to early modern times, while its geographic coverage is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Spatial span of Bi(bli)oArch

The webpage design has been kept simple in order to facilitate user-interface interaction. The Bi(bli)oArch home page (Figure 2) provides some key information regarding this resource and basic user instructions. By clicking on *Get Started*, the users are transferred to the Search page, whereby they can conduct their bibliographic search (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Bi(bli)oArch Home page

Region

Keyword

Year From # Year To #

SEARCH

TITLE %	YEAR %	JOURNAL/BOOK %	DOI	AUTHORS	REGION	KEYWORD	EXPORT
Skeleton found in Shaft No 42 of the uninscribed Mastaba 'B'	1953	In: Abu Bakr AM (ed.) Excavations at Giza 1949-1950. Cairo: Government Press, 85		Abadir F	Egypt	Pathology	+ X
Latest tomb findings at Leptis Magna and in the vicinity	1995	Libya Antiqua ns 1: 154-155		Abd al-Rahman AS	Libya	No Keyword	+ X
A human skull with multiple unusual anomalies	1960	Alexandria Medical Journal 6(3): 300-306		Abdel-Malek S, Mikhail Y	Egypt	Pathology	+ X

Figure 3. Part of Bi(bli)oArch Search page

Bi(bli)oArch allows bibliographic search by region and theme. The regional search adopts modern-day national borders, even though we acknowledge that these borders had little to no meaning in the past. For simplicity, the term ‘Levant’ has been used to jointly denote countries along the Levantine coast and Jordan, while ‘Arabian Peninsula’ has been used to represent Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and Yemen. The option ‘No Region’ is also available for users not wishing to restrict their search geographically.

The thematic division of the entries (‘keywords’) uses the following broad bioarchaeological themes:

- Activity
- Ancient DNA
- Biodistance
- Demography
- Diet
- Isotopes
- Metrics
- Mobility
- Nonmetrics
- Pathology
- Stature
- Taphonomy

The above themes represent both keywords linked to aspects of past skeletal biology (Activity, Biodistance, Demography, Diet, Mobility, Pathology, Stature, Taphonomy) but also methods for addressing these aspects (Ancient DNA, Isotopes, Metrics, Nonmetrics). This was a conscious choice aimed at accommodating different types of bibliographic research. Note that users may choose to combine keywords, such as ‘Isotopes’ and ‘Diet’, since multiple keywords and regions

can be simultaneously selected for a more advanced search. The option ‘No Keyword’ is also available. As the above keywords may be defined in different ways by different scholars, please note that ‘Activity’ encompassed all papers on enthesal changes, cross-sectional geometric properties or other skeletal indicators of mechanical stress (e.g. Schmorl’s nodes, osteoarthritis); ‘Ancient DNA’ included biomolecular studies, usually examining ancestry or pathogen DNA but also DNA preservation; ‘Biodistance’ included all studies reporting the results of (metric or nonmetric) biodistance analysis as well as papers that presented nonmetric traits without embedding them in a biodistance analysis; ‘Demography’ covered all papers that reported any information of the age-at-death and sex of the skeletons under study, even if these were not palaeodemographically analyzed; ‘Diet’ encompassed studies on dental wear, dental diseases and isotope data ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$); ‘Isotopes’ studies included both mobility and dietary studies ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$); ‘Metrics’ encompassed any study providing metric data (biodistance, stature, isolated measurements); ‘Mobility’ involved biodistance and isotope studies ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$); ‘Nonmetrics’ covered all biodistance studies employing nonmetric traits as well as papers that presented isolated cranial, dental or postcranial traits; ‘Pathology’ included papers on any pathological condition irrespective of etiology and diagnostic method (e.g. macroscopic, histological, genetic); ‘Stature’ encompassed papers on stature estimation; ‘Taphonomy’ covered all papers that included any information regarding the preservation of the remains.

The users may specify the publication date of the works they are interested in, using the boxes ‘Year From’ and ‘Year To’. We are currently working on adding the option to also search the entries per time period (e.g. Neolithic, Bronze Age).

Once the search terms are defined, users should click on *Search* and a few seconds later the list of entries matching their search criteria will appear under the *Search* button. Note that, by default, the Search page provides the list of all entries in the Bi(bli)oArch database under the *Search* button and this is subsequently narrowed down once specific search criteria have been user-defined. The results are organized alphabetically by the first authors’ last name. However, the users may reorder them alphabetically by journal/book title or publication title, or by year of publication (starting from the oldest date). For all entries that are not in English, the titles and abstracts (when available) have been translated to English and are provided along with the originals. Please note that whenever the authors of the original entries had provided an English translation of the title and/or the abstract, we opted to use it rather than translate the text anew, even though in some cases this entailed syntax/grammar errors. Whenever available, the DOI is also provided so that users can retrieve more easily the publications via the publishers’ websites. Even though every effort has been made to access all works listed in the database, in certain cases this was not possible. In such cases, the papers have been tagged as ‘No Region’ or ‘No Keyword’ unless the region and/or theme were clear from the publication title. If no search terms are input, all available titles will be given in the output list.

The number of visible entries per page can be adjusted from 10 to 1000. By clicking on the title of the entries that appear in blue bold font, a new window pops up with the abstract of the publication so that users can assess whether indeed this work is of interest to them. The users can add in a list the entries they are interested in by clicking on the + button at the far right of each entry. Similarly,

they may remove entries from their list by clicking the X button. Alternatively, they may add all entries that resulted from their search by clicking on *ADD ALL* at the bottom of the search results. Once they have selected the entries that are most relevant to them, they can download the list in portable document format (PDF) or tab delimited values format (TSV) using the buttons *DOWNLOAD PDF* or *DOWNLOAD TSV*, respectively, at the bottom of the search results. The TSV option should be easily read by Notepad (Windows) and/or Text Editor (Mac), while Supplement 3 provides simple stepwise instructions for inputting the TSV file to Excel.

3. Broad trends in EMME bioarchaeological publications

This section presents the number of publications in the Bi(bli)oArch database per region, theme and year of publication. Some broad patterns emerging from these descriptive statistics will be briefly outlined; however, they should be treated with caution since we cannot assess how many more publications are available and have not been identified by our team yet.

With regard to the geographic distribution of the publications (Figure 4), the Levant and Egypt are the most systematically examined regions from a bioarchaeological perspective, followed by Greece and Turkey, and then Cyprus, Iran and the Arabian Peninsula, while Iraq and Libya are the least studied regions.

Figure 4. Heat map representing the number of bioarchaeological papers per region

As expected, there is an overall upward trend in the number of bioarchaeological publications per decade, with the number of papers more than doubling from 1991-2000 to 2001-2010 (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Total number of papers in Bi(bli)oArch per decade of publication

Figure 6. Total number of papers in Bi(bli)oArch by theme

Among the publications where we could access the full papers and assess the aspects of skeletal biology covered, the great majority included different aspects of palaeopathology. Studies containing demographic information were the second most common, followed by publications containing metric data, biodistances, taphonomic information and diet. Studies encompassing

isotopes analyses or nonmetric traits, as well as studies examining stature and activity patterns were very similar in frequency. Finally, mobility studies and papers employing ancient DNA analysis were the least common, which can be attributed to the fact that the analytical methods primarily adopted in these studies (isotopes and aDNA) have been developed rather recently. Note that the total number of papers emerging from Figure 6 is much higher than 3,521 because most papers covered multiple themes, thus they have been counted several times (once per covered theme). The broad patterns of Figure 6 are not only seen overall in the EMME but largely reflect the trends within each region under examination (Table 1). Once again, the total sum of papers in Table 1 does not exactly match that of Figure 6 because certain papers covered more than one region and have been thus counted several times.

Table 1. References in Bi(bli)oArch by theme and country

Theme	Egypt	Levant	Turkey	Greece	Cyprus	Arabian Peninsula	Iran	Iraq	Libya
Ancient DNA	21	27	19	21	4	2	6	0	2
Mobility	14	40	17	22	4	12	9	0	3
Activity	42	67	43	38	12	15	10	7	4
Nonmetrics	63	62	60	32	17	7	10	4	5
Stature	43	47	88	57	10	11	8	0	1
Isotopes	28	63	37	95	7	10	13	3	2
Diet	56	100	62	124	11	18	17	7	1
Taphonomy	31	131	68	125	19	30	29	8	2
Biodistance	231	76	91	56	28	7	21	11	7
Metrics	222	111	146	76	21	19	29	10	5
Demography	123	193	193	171	37	43	40	14	4
Pathology	406	303	284	263	59	69	63	22	8

The above patterns exhibit some interesting parallels and differences to those observed in human osteological research worldwide, as attested though the publications in the American Journal of Physical Anthropology between 1980 and 2000 (Stojanowski and Buikstra, 2005). The categories used in the meta-analysis conducted by Stojanowski and Buikstra (2005) are rather different to the ones adopted here, thus no direct comparison can be conducted. Nonetheless, both studies found pathology to be the most commonly published topic and biodistance analysis to be popular. A notable difference is that demography and taphonomy were the least common topics published in the American Journal of Physical Anthropology, whereas they are among the common topics in EMME bioarchaeology. This apparent discrepancy can be attributed to the different criteria used in each study in order to classify publications as conveying data on demography and taphonomy. In the current study, as explained above, we considered a paper as conveying demographic information if any data on the age-at-death and sex distribution of the assemblages was provided, whether a formal palaeodemographic analysis was conducted or not. Similarly, we classified under ‘taphonomy’ both papers that were explicitly methodologically focused on taphonomic processes

and their skeletal impact but also all papers that made reference to the state of preservation of the remains.

The patterns observed based on the current Bi(bli)oArch entries also match those seen in bioarchaeology in the UK between 2001 and 2007 (Mays, 2010), with pathology being again the most common theme, followed by ‘normal skeletal variation’, which encompasses metrics and nonmetric traits. In the case of the UK, demography is not an uncommon theme and it has been defined the same way as in Bi(bli)oArch. Finally, until 1995 the least common studies were the ones employing aDNA and isotopic analysis, as expected, but these topics/methods witnessed an increase in 2001-2007.

4. Future development

Bi(bli)oArch aspires to continuously expand in order to reflect the ever-increasing human bioarchaeological literature. Our team is systematically monitoring the publication of new works using the search means described in section 2 and will be updating Bi(bli)oArch at regular intervals. At the same time, we are working towards accessing the full publication for the papers for which at the moment we only have the title info; hence, we could not safely attribute them to a regional or thematic category. This latter initiative is currently restricted by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has resulted in very limited physical library access; nonetheless, it is anticipated to resume in the following months. This project will be sustained in the long term by being embedded within the activities of the Leventis Chair in Archaeological Sciences at the Cyprus Institute, an initiative funded by the A.G. Leventis Foundation, focused on developing the broad spectrum of archaeological sciences in Cyprus and the wider eastern Mediterranean. We would be deeply grateful if you could bring to our attention corrections and omissions so that Bi(bli)oArch evolves into a cooperative initiative. You may contact us either directly by email (e.nikita@cyi.ac.cy; m.mardini@cyi.ac.cy) or using the *Submissions/Feedback* option in the Bi(bli)oArch website.

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Supplementary material

Supplement 1. Web database Architecture

Supplement 2. List of journals containing papers represented in Bi(bli)oArch

Supplement 3. Instructions for inputting TSV files in Excel

References

Creswell, J.W., Creswell, J.D. 2018. *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*, fifth ed. SAGE Publications, Thousand Oaks.

Katz, M.J. 2009. *From Research to Manuscript: A Guide to Scientific Writing*. Springer, New York.

Larsen, C.S. 2015. *Bioarchaeology: Interpreting Behavior from the Human Skeleton*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

Leppard, T.P., Esposito, C., Esposito, M. 2020. The bioarchaeology of migration in the ancient Mediterranean: meta-analysis of radiogenic ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$) isotope ratios. *J. Mediterr. Archaeol.* 33, 211-241. <https://doi.org/10.1558/jma.18784>

Mays, S. 2010. Human osteoarchaeology in the UK 2001–2007: A bibliometric perspective. *Int. J. Osteoarchaeol.* 20, 192–204. <https://doi.org/10.1002/oa.1021>

Müller, A., Hussein, K. 2017. Meta-analysis of teeth from European populations before and after the 18th century reveals a shift towards increased prevalence of caries and tooth loss. *Arch. Oral Biol.* 73, 7-15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archoralbio.2016.08.018>

Nikita, E. 2017. *Osteoarchaeology: A Guide to the Macroscopic Study of Human Skeletal Remains*. Academic Press, San Diego.

Setzer, T.J. 2014. Malaria detection in the field of paleopathology: A meta-analysis of the state of the art. *Acta Trop.* 140, 97-104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actatropica.2014.08.010>

Steckel, R.H., Rose, J.C., Larsen, C.S., Walker, P.L., 2002. Skeletal health in the Western Hemisphere from 4000 B.C. To the Present. *Evol. Anthropol.* 11, 142-155.

Steckel, R.H., Rose, J.C., 2002. *The Backbone of History: Health and Nutrition in the Western Hemisphere*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

Stojanowski, C.M., Buikstra, J.E. 2005. Research trends in human osteology: A content analysis of papers published in the *American Journal of Physical Anthropology*. *Am. J. Phys. Anthropol.* 128, 98–109. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.20088>